

An Epidemiological Study on Investigation of Vector Indices and Migration Pattern of Aedes Mosquito in a Dengue Outbreak in an Urban Habitat in North 24 Parganas District of West Bengal

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Abstract:

Background: Investigation of Dengue outbreaks play a big role to ascertain the behaviour and migration pattern of Aedes mosquito. Entomological investigation is based largely on larval indices. However, there is weak association between these indices and viral transmission, because these threshold indices also differ from place to places. It is recommended to find an area-specific re-evaluation of the utility of larval indices.

Materials and Methods: This study aimed at to study the migration pattern of infected Aedes mosquito and relationship of vector indices with occurrence of outbreak. This is a observational study on investigation of a dengue outbreak in an urban habitat in a North 24 Parganas of West Bengal. The period of study was done in August and September 2021. Data was collected by house-to-house team of the municipality and subsequently analysed by District entomologists. House Index, Container Index, Bratue Index and Pupal Index are considered as study variables. Diagram was drawn on Microsoft office power point for illustration of movement of focus of outbreak with time.

Results: House Index was observed to be highest just before the upsurge of the cases. It is found to be most sensitive index among all larval indices. Container Index did not reflect any change during the outbreak. Breatue Index did not collaborate with the occurrence of outbreak. Pupal Index is also found to be as sensitive as House Index.

Conclusions: Diagrammatic presentation based on vector indices may guide the public health personnel to predict the cluster formation of Dengue outbreak in advance.

Keywords: Aedes, Dengue, Outbreak, Migration, Indices.

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Introduction

Dengue Virus causes Dengue fever is considered as an acute mosquito-borne viral infection. Dengue Fever is presently considered the world's most important re-emerging arboviral disease with over 50% of the world's population at risk of developing the disease. [1] Approximately 3.6 billion people are currently at risk of dengue infection in over 100 countries of Asia, Americas and Africa. [2] It has been estimated that 390 million dengue infections occur worldwide annually. [3] In India, there were 136422 cases and 132 deaths due to Dengue in 2019. [4] The dengue virus, a member of the genus Flavivirus of the family Flaviviridae, is an arthropod-borne virus that includes four different serotypes (DEN-1, DEN-2, DEN-3, and DEN-4). [5,6] Females are predominantly infected with dengue

viruses after biting a viraemic human. Vertical transmission between generations also may occur to an extent, although its significance is debated. [7] It was observed by many researchers that it takes between 5 and 33 days at 25 °C, with a mean of 15 days, for viruses to multiply, mature, and migrate to the salivary glands before the mosquito can transmit the virus to another person. [8] This virus is known worldwide to cause many outbreaks. Investigation of outbreaks play a big role to ascertain the behaviour and migration pattern of Aedes mosquito. This entomological investigation is based largely on larval indices ie, container index (CI), house index (HI) and Breatue index (BI). The Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) and World Health Organization (WHO) have described

threshold levels for dengue transmission as low HI<0.1%, medium HI 0.1%–5% and high HI>5%. However, there is weak association between these indices and viral transmission, [9,10] Hence utilisation of these indicators are limited to presence or absence of vector in those areas. [11] Because these threshold indices also differ from place to places [12], recent studies have recommended an area-specific re-evaluation of the utility of larval indices. [13] Dengue-infected human movements should be considered as another important factor since Aedes generally has a short flight range so is unlikely to spread dengue over large distances. [14] So designing most appropriate intervention to contain the epidemic is a great challenge to the public health personnel. It is seen that, Aedes is a day time feeder and can fly up to a limited distance of 400 meters. [15] Some aspects of adult mosquito behaviour and mosquito ecology contribute significantly in determining the capacity of vector populations to transmit pathogens. Migration pattern of infected Aedes within a transmission area, period of transmission, shifting of cluster of active cases are the important areas that should to be clearly understood by the members of the vector borne disease control team of the district so that, timely suitable measures to control dengue can be made.

Aims and Objectives: This study aimed to study the migration pattern of infected Aedes mosquito and relationship of vector indices with occurrence of outbreak.

Subjects and Methods: This is an Observational study on investigation of a dengue outbreak in an urban habitat in a North 24 Parganas of West Bengal.

Study Site- The study was done at Madhyamgram municipality in the district of North 24 Paraganas of West Bengal, India. The municipality has a population of 1,96,127. It has 28 wards and 4 Urban Primary Health Centres. The outbreak actually took place in ward no 12.

Study Period- The period of study was done in August and September 2021.

Data Collection: Under IDSP (Integrated Disease Surveillance Project), data is collected on epidemic prone diseases on weekly basis (Monday to Sunday) from all blocks and municipalities of the district. Early Warning Signals (EWS) is generated by District IDSP Cell based on the comparison of cases in the corresponding week of the previous year.

Data was collected by house-to-house team of the municipality and subsequently analysed by District IDSP cell.

Study Variables:

Description of Variables-

House Index (HI)= (Number of infested houses/Number of houses inspected) × 100

Container Index (CI) = (Number of positive containers/Number of containers examined) × 100

Breatue Index (BI) = (Number of positive containers/Number of houses inspected) × 100

Pupal Index- total number of pupae found, divided by the total number of inspected households. A case of Dengue is defined as anybody who has been detected NS1 and/ or IgM antibody by ELISA for Dengue in the blood

Data Analysis-Data was checked for completeness and entered into excel sheets. Diagram was drawn on Microsoft office power point for illustration of movement of focus of outbreak with time.

Results

Chronology of Epidemic: Under IDSP, data is collected on epidemic prone diseases on weekly basis (Monday to Sunday). It has been found that there is a tendency of upsurge of dengue cases occur during mid-June to mid- November in West Bengal. During IDSP Week 35-37 in Ward number 12 of Madhyamgram municipality, the Index case for Dengue was detected on 23 rd August 2021. Subsequently 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th cases were identified very close to the Index case (Diagram 1).

During this time period the vector indices were found to be HI: 21.95%, CI: 27.17%, BI: 60.98 PI: 17. On 37th IDSP week 6th, 7th, 8th cases were identified to the west of the Initial Dengue Cluster on which was initiated from 29 th August 2021. Thereafter 9th, 10th, 11th, 12th, 18th, 20th, 21st cases were identified in the same area during IDSP week 37-39, confirming the second cluster. So, the Initial Dengue Cluster was shifted/ extended to the West of Ward number 12. In this period the vector indices were found to be HI: 33.33%, CI: 27.14%, BI: 52.78, PI: 19.44% (Diagram 2). Small containers like discarded plastic containers, thermocol made articles, water storage drum, domestic wastes, crevices of tripal sheets, lift basement and open septic pits at construction sites were the major larval sources, where House to house survey workers and Vector Control teams of Madhyamgram Municipality were involved for intensified larval source reduction activities. The similar types of containers were identified as larval sources at 2nd cluster area and the similar preventive actions i.e. larval source reduction were taken.

As the Index case had no history of migration, therefore it can be assumed that, transmission was started locally. A nearby construction site was spotted with numerous breeding spots where the infected Aedes mosquitoes got a good opportunity to multiply. Subsequently numerous larvae of Aedes were found at the same period in that particular

site. From that construction site few infected adult Aedes had started shifting towards the North-east part of Ward number 12 and was responsible for the initiation of third cluster. During this period the vector indices were HI: 37.50%, CI: 32%, BI: 100, PI: 12.50%.

Subsequently 13th, 14th, 15th, 16th, 17th, 19th and 22th cases were found on the North- east side of the Initial Dengue Cluster during IDSP week 38-39 from 25.09. 2021. This cluster of cases may be defined as third cluster. So, it may be inferred that the second Dengue Cluster was extended to the North-east part of Ward number 12 during that period with a vector index of HI: 8.11%, CI: 27.78%, BI: 13.51, PI: 2.70%. The last diagnosed case was reported within 50 meters from the Initial Cluster. It reiterated the fact of low flying zone of the Aedes mosquito. Actual plotting of the cases was beneficial to mitigate the risk of evolvement of the outbreak by careful utilisation of resources in controlling the epidemic. The final shift and 3rd Cluster was formed around a construction site named “Rishi Ventoso” which is nearly 50-60 metre away from the 2nd cluster area. Huge larval source found at the under-construction underpass

area and lift space and larvicidal spraying activities gradually reduced the cases. No adulticide/fogging activity was done at these affected areas. The larval control measure (source reduction) was continued at all the cluster areas which resulted in reduction of case load.

Mosquito Index and Intervention:

As illustrated in Diagram 2 Dengue larval indices were closely followed up in the various phases of outbreak from start to peak and then to resolution. These indices helped to identify, monitor and intervene the outbreak in the municipality.

House Index was observed to be above baseline of 20 which showed rise and fall in observed weeks. It showed a decline with various interventions. House Index was observed to be highest just before the upsurge of the cases. It is found to be most sensitive index among all larval indices. Container Index did not reflect any change during the outbreak. Breteau Index did not collaborate with the occurrence of outbreak. Pupal Index showed also rise just before the epidemic. This index is also found to be as sensitive as House Index.

Diagram 1: Diagram showing shift of Dengue outbreak with time

Diagram 2: Diagram showing fluctuation larval indices and incidence of dengue cases with time

Discussion

With worldwide dengue transmission reaching an all-time high, predicting dengue outbreaks in advance of their occurrence or identifying specific locations where outbreak risks are considerable are of highest importance. Fluctuations in vector indices might be used to predict advance warning of impending dengue outbreaks. Common practice is to focus on local government-level records for the dengue case data, a practice that potentially introduces error or bias for number of reasons.

In this case the data obtained from the municipality was found to be reliable to a large extent in predicting the outbreaks. Analysis and diagrammatic representation of the cases helped to predict the shifting of the cluster of cases during the outbreak. Diagrammatic representation was based on larval indices and plotting of the cases. But, Scott et al opined that less importance to be given on larval indices and greater emphasis should be placed on relative abundance of adult vectors in relation to human serotype-specific herd immunity, introduction of unique viruses, mosquito-human contact and weather. Pictorial presentation may help the ground level managers of the public health managers to judiciously plan to allocate resources for optimal utilisation.

In various studies, the size of such clusters ranged from 800 m to less than 100 m. [17,18] In this case the shift is restricted to 300-400 metre. Not only the vector indices, the occurrence, size and migration of the outbreak is also influenced by other factors.

The other factors for formation of clusters may be determined by dispersal of the vector which itself can vary over time, and is influenced by house density and by human movement within and beyond the infection cluster. [17-20] On the contrary, It is also noted in some studies that because mosquito vectors are mobile and many bite at night, the prevalent assumption for vector-borne diseases has been that local human movements play only a nominal role in transmission. [21] In this study the subsequent cluster formation was noticed in adjacent to primary cluster. It may indicate the lesser role of human migration in cluster formation.

There are evidences that Dengue outbreak is not dependant on vector indices but but other factors too. In Trinidad, West Indies, the incidence of Dengue fever was 5.05 cases/1000 populations in 2002, largely as the result of a major outbreak, but declined to 0.49 case/1000 in 2004. The monthly Breteau indices (BI) did not decline over the 3-year study period, however, but increased from a mean of 29 in 2002 to 36 in 2004. The apparent decline in dengue transmission since 2002 appears to be largely attributable to the development of 'herd immunity' in the general population. [22] It is also observed that vector indices might be diluted by inclusion of neighbouring areas with low densities, thus masking any true relationships. [22] The vector density, below which dengue transmission does not occur, continues to be a topic of much debate and conflicting empiric evidence. For example, dengue outbreaks occurred in Singapore when the national overall HI was <1%. [23] In contrast, re-

searchers from Fortaleza, Brazil, found that dengue outbreaks never occurred when HI was <1%. [24] However, different geographic levels are used to calculate the indices in the various studies, and the appropriated level for entomological indices is in itself an issue of debate. [25] But in this study, the incidence of outbreak largely correlated to the fluctuation of vector indices. Training on accurate measurement of larval indices by health workers may go a long way in predicting the shifting of the clusters in an outbreak.

Conclusion

Diagrammatic presentation based on vector indices may guide the public health personnel to predict the cluster formation of Dengue outbreak in advance. This will ensure the optimal utilisation of resources. Training of the health workers may ensure the accurate measurement of vector indices. Analysis of indices at the grass root level and plotting of the cases may result in containment of the outbreak.

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